

Form tion of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part V.
Condensation of *cyclo*Hexylidenecyclo-
hexanone with Cyanoacetamide.

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As hexahydro-2-quinolone synthesised by one of us (Sen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1351) has been found to be a powerful bactericide, further synthesis of analogous quinoline derivatives seemed to be of more than ordinary synthetic interest. The *cyclo*hexylidenecyclohexanones appeared to provide a class of suitable starting material for this purpose, as the conjugated double-bonded system in these compounds offers an easy means of synthesising quinolone, by condensing them with cyanoacetamide in the presence of sodium ethoxide or piperidine (*loc. cit.*). A further extension of such condensation may be made with hydroxymethyleneketones derived from these *cyclo*hexylidenecyclohexanones, which do not appear to have been prepared and investigated before. The therapeutic value of these compounds is now under investigation, whilst below is given a description of the experimental work performed in this connection. The quinolone derivatives were formed according to the following scheme:

EXPERIMENTAL.

*Condensation of cyclo*Hexylidenecyclohexanone with Cyanoacetamide in the Presence of Sodium Ethoxide.—Dry hydrogen chloride was passed into *cyclo*-hexanone (50 g.) at 0°. After leaving overnight the hydrogen chloride was expelled by heating on the sand-bath and the residual liquid subjected to vacuum distillation. The

fraction collecting at 150-153°/20 mm. was pure *cyclohexylidene-cyclohexanone* (26 g.), identified by its oxime and semicarbazone. The solid compound with hydrogen chloride described by Wallace (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 70) could not be isolated.

Metallic sodium (0.52 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol was added to a solution of cyanacetamide (1.9 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol. To the mixture so obtained, *cyclohexylidene-cyclohexanone* (4 g.) dissolved also in absolute alcohol was gradually added with occasional shaking, and the whole kept overnight. Next day, carbon dioxide was passed into the mixture, and the solid that separated out was filtered and washed with absolute alcohol. The solid product was boiled with water when a white residue (1 g.) was left behind. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 340-341°. (Found: N, 11.19. $C_{15}H_{20}ON_2$ requires N, 11.47 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the product with fuming hydrochloric acid or 80% sulphuric acid gave either the unchanged substance or decomposition products from which no crystalline pure compound could be isolated.

4-Methyl-cyclohexylidene-4-methyl-cyclohexanone was prepared by passing dry hydrogen chloride into 4-methyl *cyclohexanone* as usual. It boils at 170-172°/5 mm. Yield, 26 g. of the purified product from 46 g. of the ketone. The compound was previously prepared by Marcel Godehot and Fedox Taboury (*Compt. rend.*, 1919, 169, 1169) by passing the vapour of 4-methylcyclohexanone over heated calcium oxide. The identity of the two was established by the preparation of an oxime melting at 153-154°.

The condensation product from the above unsaturated ketone and cyanacetamide in the presence of sodium ethoxide was obtained as above and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 295-297°. (Found: N, 10.48. $C_{17}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 10.29 per cent.).

8-Methyl-8-cyclohexylidene-8-methylcyclohexane-8-one prepared by passing dry hydrogen chloride into 8-methylcyclohexanone boils at 165-166°/20 mm. Yield 30 g. from 50 g. of the ketone.

The condensation product of this ketone with cyanacetamide in the presence of sodium ethoxide, isolated as indicated in the case of the other isomer, crystallised from acetic acid, melting at 326-328°. (Found: N, 10.18. $C_{17}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 10.29 per cent.).

Condensation of Hydromethylencyclohexylidene-cyclohexanone with Cyanacetamide in the Presence of Piperidine.

Hydromethylene cyclohexylidene-cyclohexanone.—*cyclohexylidene-cyclohexanone* (19 g.) was mixed with amyl formate

(11 g.) and dry ether (100 c.c.). Metallic sodium (2.2 g.) in the form of wire was then added to the solution slowly with frequent disintegration of the incrustation on the sodium by means of a stout glass rod. The mixture was kept in ice during the experiment and allowed to stand overnight. The sodium salt of the hydroxymethylene derivative which separated out, was dissolved in water and the solution separated from the ethereal layer containing the unacted formate and cyclohexylidenecyclohexanone as also some amyl alcohol. The aqueous solution was extracted with some more ether, and then acidified with dilute acetic acid in the cold when an oil separated. The oil was extracted with ether, dried over ignited sodium sulphate and distilled in vacuum. The liquid (7 g.) distilled at 170-172°/15 mm. It gave a violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 75.24; H, 8.98. $C_{13}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 75.73; H, 8.73 per cent.).

The copper salt was formed when the hydroxymethylene compound was digested with a saturated solution of copper acetate for 4 hours on the water-bath. A solid separated which when crystallised from absolute alcohol melted at 174-175°. (Found: Cu, 13.27. $C_{26}H_{34}O_4Cu$ requires Cu, 13.1 per cent.).

The pyrazole derivative prepared by the action of semicarbazide hydrochloride in the presence of fused sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid, melted at 258° after crystallisation from acetic acid. The product dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and was regenerated by alkali. It is sparingly soluble in almost all organic solvents. (Found: N, 13.76. $C_{13}H_{18}N_2$ requires N, 13.86 per cent.).

The condensation of the hydroxymethylene compound with cyanoacetamide was brought in the usual way (*cf. Sen, loc. cit.*). Crystals began to separate after one hour, but the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight. Crystallised twice from acetic acid using animal charcoal, the substance melted at 230-232°. The product was insoluble in water, dissolved in caustic soda, and exhibited violet fluorescence in alcohol and acetic acid solutions. It absorbed bromine, indicating the presence of the double bond at the cyclohexylidene junction. (Found: C, 75.18; H, 7.27; N, 11.43. $C_{16}H_{18}ON_2$ requires C, 75.59; H, 7.08; N, 11.02 per cent.).

Hydroxymethylene-4-methyl(4'-methylcyclohexylidene)-6-cyclohexanone prepared as above boiled at 180°/11 mm. Yield 7 g. from 20 g. of the ketone. (Found: C, 77.0; H, 9.29. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 76.92; H, 9.4 per cent.).

The *pyrazole* derivative prepared as usual melted at 262-263°. It dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and was sparingly soluble in almost all organic solvents. (Found: N, 12.08. $C_{15}H_{22}N_2$ requires N, 12.17 per cent.).

The condensation product with cyanoacetamide obtained as usual, crystallised from acetic acid in plates, m. p. 243-244°. It absorbed bromine, dissolved in caustic soda and exhibited fluorescence in alcoholic solution. (Found: N, 10.15. $C_{18}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 9.98 per cent.).

Condensation of Acetyl cyclohexylidene cyclohexanone with Cyanoacetamide.—Acetyl cyclohexylidene cyclohexanone was prepared in the usual way by condensing cyclohexylidene cyclohexanone (25 g.) with ethyl acetate (80 g.) and metallic sodium (8.25 g.). The fraction distilling at 170-180°/20 mm. was redistilled when a liquid (10 g.) boiling at 170-175°/20 mm. was obtained. The liquid was not pure, and no definite copper salt could be isolated. It gave a violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, characteristic of β -diketones. But an oxime could be separated melting at 145-147° which corresponded to that of cyclohexylidene cyclohexanone. It seemed, therefore, that the liquid was a mixture of cyclohexylidene cyclohexanone and acetyl cyclohexylidene cyclohexanone. On condensing, however, the impure liquid with cyanoacetamide in the presence of piperidine in the usual way a product melting at 245-246° was obtained which absorbs bromine. The condensation conducted in the presence of sodium ethoxide and absolute alcohol gave rise to two products. Into the condensation mixture, carbon dioxide was passed and the total solid thus separated, was boiled with absolute alcohol and filtered. From the filtrate a solid could be separated which when crystallised from alcohol melted at 245-246° and was identical with the product obtained when the condensation was effected in the presence of piperidine. The residue on the filter was next boiled with water when a white residue was left behind. Crystallising from acetic acid, it melted at 340-341° and was identical with the product obtained by condensing cyclohexylidene cyclohexanone with cyanoacetamide. It did not absorb bromine as expected. (Found: N, 10.64. $C_{17}H_{20}ON_2$ requires N, 10.45 per cent.).